

Exploring the Benefits and the Characteristics of Selected Genres of Music

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Abstract - *This study specifically described the profile of the respondents in terms of age, gender and grade level; identified the importance of music; determined the level of awareness on the different genres of music; and tested the significant difference in the level of awareness when grouped according to profile variables.*

Three hundred five (305) respondents participated in the study. Fifteen to sixteen respondents of each grade level (Grade 7, 8, 9 and 10) and 20 teachers participated in the study. Result showed that music provides a sense of achievement, happiness, and satisfaction to the respondents. Among the five (5) different genre of music, they are more aware on rock music as millennials who are more exposed to this kind of music. Female is more adept in distinguishing the sounds and different genres of music.

Keywords: *Genres, Pop Music, Rhythm and Blues, Classical Music, Rock Music and Rap Music*

INTRODUCTION

Greatest music consists of people singing with their voices or playing melodic instruments, such as the piano, guitar, or drums. Music is sound that has been systematized by means of rhythm, melody or harmony. Example, if somebody knocks glasses while eating, it makes noise. If a person knocks glasses in a rhythmic way, they are creating a modest kind of music too abrupt.

According to Dorrell (2010) an expert expressed that, the mechanics like, the song, notes, mood, beat, instruments, harmonies, agreement, and bass would likely join to deliver great music. Furthermore, it is likewise partitioned into disparate classifications or sorts that separate one style from another. These kinds can be isolated by the instruments included and how they are finished. There is additionally a social or social element that aided in their development as a different kind, because of every type being performed in a marginally assorted manner.

Music is for all ages, but some teenagers nowadays are exposed too much with music of different genres. Since they are still young, their choice of genres sometimes is affected by their environment, peer group or the members of the family.

Music is an essential subject in schools because it bonds the instruments at home and in the community, who listen responsively to the diversity of music with appreciation and a serious ear, who support the hard work of others to make music, and who share their harmonious awareness with family and friends. Meanwhile, the subject contains both ideas to be educated and skills to be established. A meaningful

program of study should take in common teaching with class time programmed during the school day. And that in a way that it affords for long period student involvement, earning and accomplishment, the program will be continued throughout the school years.

As Secondary Education students who will be a teacher someday, the need to have more knowledge on the awareness of the students to music because the teacher contributes a lot in the achievement of a student in music. Help students to discover, improve, create and improvise music. In addition, it is important for the teachers to know the interest and likes of the students.

The researchers conducted this study because as a future Mapeh majors, it is a part of our responsibility to know what genre of music catches the interest of our students. That despite today's generation, that the technology is very high, the researchers wanted to know if the students of 20th century are still aware of the different genres of music.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The study aimed to describe the profile of the respondents in terms of age and gender and grade level; identified the benefits of music; determined the level of awareness on the different genres of music; and tested the significant difference on the level of awareness when grouped according to profile variables.

METHODS

Design

This study used the descriptive method utilized a subject in the questionnaire, to describe the profile, to identify the different genres, and the significant difference between the profile variable and awareness on music. Different genres included pop music, country music and last is rhythm and blues.

Descriptive research is a helpful technique for social occasion data about uncommon marvels that couldn't be repeated in a lab or about subjects that are not surely knew. It doesn't test particular connections between factors, be that as it may, they give data about practices and properties with the objective of achieving a superior comprehension of a given theme (Best & Kahn, 2006).

Participants

Year Level	Number of students
Grade 7	61
Grade 8	64
Grade 9	71
Grade 10	109
Total	305

Instrument

The study used a self-made questionnaire. The questionnaire was validated by an expert in music and underwent pilot testing reliability administered to 15 students. The result of the pilot test was submitted to the university statistician for approval. This includes Part I, the profile variables. Part II, the importance of music. Part III, the level of awareness on the different genres of music.

Procedures

The researchers conducted a pilot testing reliability administered to 15 students. They proposed a letter to ask a permission to distribute the questionnaire to 305 students of a private university in the Philippines. Then, researchers distributed the questionnaire to the respondents. Some of the students from grade 10 refuse to answer the questionnaire, but instead of forcing them to answer they look for other students that will answer the questionnaire voluntarily. After they collected the questionnaire and tallied the result. After tallying they submitted the result to the university statistician. The result was explained and analyzed by the researchers, and hand over to their adviser to be checked. After the final defense the researcher revise the study based on the comments and suggestions of their panelists.

Data Analysis

All data gathered were be tallied, encoded and interpreted using different statistical tools such as frequency distribution, weighted mean and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). These tools be based on the objectives of the study. The data were treated using statistical software, PASW version to further analyze the results of the study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Percentage Distribution of the Respondents' Profile

Profile Variables	Frequenc y	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	132	43.30
Female	173	56.70
Age		
17-19 years old	4	1.30
14-16 years old	202	66.20
11 – 13 years old	99	32.50
Year Level		
Grade 7	61	20.00
Grade 8	64	21.00
Grade 9	71	23.30
Grade 10	109	35.70

The profile of the Junior High School students from Lyceum of the Philippines University-High School includes gender, age, and year level. Table 1. contains the distribution of the respondents according to their gender. Table reveals that 173 or 56.70% of the total respondents were females compared to 132 or 43.30% males.

This means that females dominated the male respondents. In terms of age, most of them fall on the age bracket of 14-16 years old which obtain the highest frequency of 202 or 66.20% it was followed by 11-13 years old with total number 99 or 32.50% respondents and the lowest frequency falls on the brocket of 17-19 years old with the total number of 4 or 1.30%. It is evident from the table that the grade 10 students form the biggest group with 109 or 35.70% of the total population of the respondents. Next to this are the grade 9 students which has 71 or 23.30% number of respondents. Grade 8 has 64 or 21% of respondents and the smallest group belongs to grade 7 that has 61 or 20% of respondents.

According to Christenson and Peterson (2011), they found that even in by and large homogenous youth gathering of spectators there were two specific culture a male and a Female. They found that males and females use and respond to music in different

ways. Dees and Vera (2010) found that music and its qualities suitable for an all-male and an all-female social event contrasted. Also, females were more probable utilize music as an optional satisfaction.

Table 2. Benefits of Music

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Music provides a sense of achievement, happiness, and satisfaction.	3.82	Strongly Agree	1
2. Music, melody, rhythm, tone color, lyrics, and harmony are a unique experience	3.72	Strongly Agree	5
3. Music helps in the release of emotions and in the expressions of one's feelings via the lines of a song or the melodic Movement of an instrumental piece.	3.82	Strongly Agree	2
4. Music is an effective means to develop nationalism, strengthen emotional discipline, and transmitting cultural values, history, and oral traditions	3.63	Strongly Agree	9.5
5. Music facilitates understanding other cultures	3.61	Strongly Agree	11.5
6. Music is used to convey ideas	3.56	Strongly Agree	13
7. Music elevates the level of artistry of performers	3.63	Strongly Agree	8
8. Music is used to communicate with God	3.66	Strongly Agree	7
9. Music is used to venerate and worship the Supreme Being	3.52	Strongly Agree	14
10. Music stirs people to noble thoughts and feelings	3.67	Strongly Agree	6
11. Music keeps workers inspired to do their best in their tasks	3.63	Strongly Agree	9.5
12. Music provide entertainment for different occasions, celebrations, and programs	3.74	Strongly Agree	3
13. Music helps to uncover musical talents	3.61	Strongly Agree	11.5
14. Music allows appreciation of musical skills	3.74	Strongly Agree	4
15. Music promotes products now in the market	3.43	Agree	15
Composite Mean	3.65	Strongly Agree	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Strongly Agree; 2.50 – 3.49 = Agree; 1.50 – 2.49 = Disagree; 1.00 – 1.49 = Strongly Disagree

Lott (2011) states that, young ladies raised to be ladylike, sustaining, and put family before work, while guys, are raised to be autonomous, focused, and put individual objectives in front of social and family thought. Subsequently, youthful male, music regularly individual and of focal significance to their lives.

As seen from the Table 2. below, the over-all assessment of the respondents strongly agreed with a composite mean of 3.65. Among the items cited, music provides a sense of achievement, happiness, and satisfaction topped on the list with a weighted mean score of 3.82 and rated strongly agree. It was followed by music helps in the release of emotions and in the expressions of one's feelings via the lines of a song or the melodic movement of an instrumental piece with the weighted mean of 3.82. Music provide entertainment for different occasions, celebrations, and programs got a weighted mean of 3.74.

According to Levitin, Davis and Palladino [6], discovered that regardless of what kind of music the psyche will inspire the feelings and it swings feelings to decide the like and abhorrence for the music.

The feelings and the music go hand and hand. It influences the most critical organ in the body, cerebrum, and it is effective device. The significance

of music has come acknowledge in more than part foundation of our selves.

On the other hand, music promotes products now in the market got the lowest mean value of 3.43 and rated agree only. Next is music used to venerate and worship the Supreme being with the weighted mean of 3.52, it was followed by music used to convey ideas which got a weighted of 3.56.

As per millennials today, they are not much interested watching television, instead they choose to use their gadgets on browsing internet and even though millennials are now focus on emotions and feelings rather than conveying ideas from the music they heard.

Table 3. Illustrates the Level of Awareness on the Different Genre of Music as to Rap Music. This shows that singers like Abra, Loonie, Andrew E, Gloc-9 and Francis Magalona the famous rappers in the Philippines got the highest weighted mean of 3.70 and verbally interpreted as fully aware. Then, it was the popularity of electronic dance music and hip-hop that made rap music extremely popular got the second highest weighted mean of 3.53 and verbally interpreted as fully aware. Next is, the lyrics are often sang fast and shouted out got the third highest

weighted mean of 3.34 and verbally interpreted as aware. Then, rap songs often can use the same pre-recorded background music but the difference in the lyrics of the song makes them stand apart from others got the fourth highest weighted mean of 3.30 and verbally interpreted as aware. And the least among the items is this rhythm is known as the flow of the rapper and is a distinguishing which got a weighed mean of 3.26 with verbal interpretation of aware.

Table 3. Level of Awareness on the Different Genre of Music as to Rap Music

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. It was the popularity of electronic dance music and hip-hop that made rap music Extremely popular	3.53	Fully Aware	2
2. Rap songs often can use the same pre-recorded background music but the difference in the lyrics of the song makes them stand apart from others.	3.30	Aware	5
3. This rhythm is known as the flow of the rapper and is a distinguishing trademark.	3.26	Aware	4
4. The lyrics are often sang fast and shouted out	3.34	Aware	3
5. Abra, Loonie, Andrew E, Gloc-9 and Francis Magalona are the famous rappers in the Philippines.	3.70	Fully Aware	1
Composite Mean	3.43	Aware	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Fully Aware; 2.50 – 3.49 = Aware; 1.50 – 2.49 = Slightly Aware; 1.00 – 1.49 = Not Aware

Generally, the level of awareness on the different genre of music as to Rap Music got the composite mean of 3.43 and verbally interpreted as Aware. This genre the least composite mean among the other genres because its lyrics are somehow violating others feeling especially women. And since our respondents are majority of women, they overruled the decision of not liking the rap music.

Much rap music, at any rate rap created by male craftsmen, runs counter to this bigger pattern. Undoubtedly, a section of rap music naturalizes certain asserted qualities of men and ladies and, as per

these ascribed contrasts, looks to limit, as opposed to widen, ladies' appropriate parts and revive male mastery. The messages are accordingly both essentialist and standardizing embracing an arrangement of direct standards for every sex's legitimate conduct toward the other and approvals for the individuals who damage these standards Weitzer and Kubrin, (2009). This can be the reason why all the genres, rap music got the lowest composite mean.

Table 4. below, illustrates the Level of Awareness on the Different Genre of Music as to Pop Music. This shows that it usually recorded and listened to on the radio or at home got the highest weighted mean of 3.65. Next is, instruments used by pop artist includes electric guitar, bass guitar, and keyboard got the second highest weighted mean of 3.62. Then, One Direction, Lady Gaga, and Little Mix are the famous pop music artists in the world got the third highest weighted mean of 3.60. Then, the lyrics of modern pop songs focus love and romantic relationships got the fourth highest weighted mean of 3.56. And the least among the items is pop music use a combination of rhythms that are dance oriented and energetic to satisfy the audience which got the weighted mean of 3.51 and all the items under the pop music is verbally interpreted as Fully Aware.

Table 4. Level of Awareness on the Different Genre of Music as to Pop Music

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. It is usually recorded and listened to on the radio or at home.	3.65	Fully Aware	1
2. One direction, Lady Gaga and little mix are the famous pop music artists in the world.	3.60	Fully Aware	3
3. The lyrics of modern pop songs focus on love and romantic relationships.	3.56	Fully Aware	4
4. Pop music uses a combination of rhythms that are dance oriented and energetic to satisfy the audience.	3.51	Fully Aware	5
5. Instruments used by pop artists include electric guitar, bass guitar, and keyboard.	3.62	Fully Aware	2
Composite Mean	3.59	Fully Aware	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Fully Aware; 2.50 – 3.49 = Aware; 1.50 – 2.49 = Slightly Aware; 1.00 – 1.49 = Not Aware

Generally, the Level of Awareness on the Different Genre of Music as to Pop Music got the composite mean of 3.59 and verbally interpreted as Fully Aware. It got the second highest composite mean because as per the millennial today, they tend to go with the trend and follow the famous artist of their ages which produces pop songs. I admit as my opinion that the pop songs of this generation can literally catch the attention of the millennials in an effortless way because majority of the singers are well known and idolized by most of the millennials.

According to Roszak (2010), numerous millennials are not yet presented to the assortment of melodic classifications that grown-ups might be. Moreover, they effectively dismiss a large number of melodic classes to lighten the estrangement more pervasive in puberty level, which is having a few reasons

Table 5. Level of Awareness on the Different Genre of Music as to Rhythm and Blues

Indicators	WM	VI	Rank
1. Rhythm and blues lyrics and melodies are related to the stories of very personal experiences in song.	3.59	Fully Aware	1
2. Drums, bass, piano or organ, and guitar are some of the most commonly used instruments.	3.58	Fully Aware	2
3. R & B deal with emotions and pain of suffering.	3.51	Fully Aware	4
4. R & B is combined elements of rhythm and blues, soul, funk, pop, hip hop, and dance.	3.45	Fully Aware	5
5. Vocalists are often known for their use of melisma, popularized by vocals such as Michael Jackson, R. Kelly, and Stevie Wonder.	3.54	Fully Aware	3
Composite Mean	3.54	Fully Aware	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Fully Aware; 2.50 – 3.49 = Aware; 1.50 – 2.49 = Slightly Aware; 1.00 – 1.49 = Not Aware

Table 5 shows the level of awareness of respondents in different genres of music as rhythm and blues, the respondents fully aware that there is an awareness on different genres of music as to rhythm and blues having an over-all composite mean 3.54. In terms the highest among was the rhythm and blues lyrics and melodies are related to the stories of very personal experiences in song was their awareness that

drums, bass, piano or organ, and guitar are some of the most commonly used instruments was the second with 3.58 mean score and has a verbal interpretation as Fully Aware of awareness. Vocalists are often known for their use of melisma, popularized by vocals such as Michael Jackson, R. Kelly, and Stevie Wonder was the third. R & B deal with emotions and pain of suffering was the fourth. The lowest was the R & B is combined elements of rhythm and blues, soul, funk, pop hip hop and dance with 3.45 mean score and Aware as the verbal interpretation.

According to Machlis and Forney (2009), R&B is known for its overwhelmingly vocal sort, highlighting an execution craftsman joined by a touch of get-together including guitar, piano, drums, acoustic bass, and tenor saxophone. As the name deduces, the style is depicted by a strong, driving beat, generally in a fourfold meter. As the effect of various styles of Rhythm and Blues, dim urban qualities have infested a wide variety of various social orders, most exceptional of contemporary Euro American youth.

Although rhythm and blues not a music most loved by numerous, it was that style is the most intense relying upon the age. It would listener be able to make you become hopelessly enamored, strike down an adversary, or sob for lost companions. Style is a wellspring of compromise, invigoration, and expectation that never comes up short. Without music in regular day to day existence, the world would be an amazingly threatening and possibly an appalling spot to be. Music has turned into the most intense blessing given by performers.

Table 6. Level of Awareness on the Different Genre of Music as to Classical Music

Indicators	WM	VI	Rank
1. Classical music is generally in written form, using staff notation, such that the performance of a piece is a literal interpretation.	3.63	FA	1
2. Embellishment by the artist is limited.			
3. Whether as accompaniment for concert performances the use of orchestral instruments is used such as wind, percussion, string and bass instruments.	3.56	FA	3
4. Use of difficult form and composition, advanced technical proficiency its artistic performance and exclusivity in taste and appeal are evident in classical music.	3.54	FA	4.5

5. Some classical era components include Joseph Hayden, Wolfgang Amadeus Mozart and Ludvig Van Beethoven.	3.54	FA	4.5
6. Classical music is noted for its use of sophisticated interpretation of musical scores of noted artists.	3.59	FA	2

Composite Mean 3.57 FA

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Fully Aware (FA); 2.50 – 3.49 = Aware; 1.50 – 2.49 = Slightly Aware; – 1.49 = Not Aware

Table 6. the level of awareness on the different genre of music as to classic music was Fully Aware with 3.57 composite mean score. Their awareness on Classical music is generally in written form, using staff notation, such that the performance of a piece is a literal interpretation. Improvisation or embellishment by the artist is limited was the highest among the parameters with Fully Aware interpretation and 3.63 mean score. Followed by 3.59 mean score in Classical music is noted for its use of sophisticated interpretation of musical scores of noted artists and a 3.56 mean score on Whether as accompaniment for concert performances that use of orchestral instruments is used such as wind, percussion, string and bass instruments as the third. However, the lowest was seen in 4.5 mean score in Use of difficult form and composition advanced.

Technical proficiency its artistic performance and exclusivity in taste and appeal are evident in classical music and some classical era composers include Joseph Hayden, Wolfgang Amadeus Mozart and Ludvig Van Beethoven.

According to Milner (2010) classical music is up 'til now a class had a great time best in its purest edge, the live execution. Classical music in the show passage states the total thought of its crowd individuals; they have set diverse activities aside to hear it. Nevertheless, a segment of the gathering of people individuals who go to indicate anterooms to hear it and a bit of the specialists who perform it there put a comparative music on while they eat or read or talk or play. These crowd individuals seem, by all accounts, to be certain that they can listen shy of what one ear to the music, which they acknowledge merits their total thought in various conditions.

Table 7. below shows the level of awareness of the students to Rock Music. As seen from the table, the over-all assessment of the respondents was verbally interpreted as fully aware with the composite mean of 3.69. This implies that the respondents are very familiar to Rock music. The results showed that most

students enjoyed listening to rock and roll music the most, whether it was hard, heavy or modern.

The indicators cited, that genre of music with a prominent vocal melody, bass guitar, and drums and Parokya ni Edgar, Spongecola, Kamikazee, Itchyworms and Rivermaya are some of the rock bands in the Philippines were tied and got a weighted mean of 3.77 and the highest number of the students' awareness. Next in rank was, usually has a strong back beat, and often revolves around the guitar, either solid electric, hollow electric, or acoustic which got a weighted mean of 3.70. This implies that the respondents are aware to rock music; its characteristics and instruments used by the artist. Listening to great rock music is fun, so that the listener catches their attention and they attracted to this genre of music its superior rock and roll taste is even better.

Table 7. Level of Awareness on the Different Genre of Music as to Rock Music

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	R ank
1. Rock music is accompanied by Electric guitar, bass guitar and drums.	3.77	Fully Aware	1.5
2. It is usually has a strong back beat and revolves around the guitar, either solid electric, hollow electric or acoustic guitar.	3.70	Fully Aware	3
3. Rock has three chords, a strong, insistent back beat and a catchy melody.	3.54	Fully Aware	5
4. A group of musicians specializing in Rock music is called rock band.	3.66	Fully Aware	4
5. Parokya ni Edgar, Spongecola, Kamikazee, Itchyworms and Rivermaya are some of the rock bands in the Philippines.	3.77	Fully Aware	1.5
Composite Mean	3.69	Fully Aware	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Fully Aware; 2.50 – 3.49 = Aware; 1.50 – 2.49 = Slightly Aware; 1.00 – 1.49 = Not Aware

Next in the rank, a group of musicians specializing in rock music is called a rock band and rock group which got a weighted mean of 3.66. On the other

hand, the lowest number of awareness of students to Rock Music was the indicator number 3, rock has three cords, a strong, insistent back beat, and a catchy melody got a weighted mean of 3.54.

Cited from the study of Gonzalez (2009) that rock and roll utilize fundamental steady rhythm and rearrange rhythms of musicality and blues to request a physical reaction and offer a test to individuals to slacken up and ease stress and stress. It has been logically demonstrated that music with a quick rhythm, and written in a noteworthy key, related accurately with the acceptance of bliss. It is no big surprise that stone and move music has, and keeps on inspiring such positive, glad, vivacious and stimulating feelings from its audience members additionally found that stone, the music of decision, made pretty much every one of the understudies' hopeful, happy, neighborly, casual and quiet.

This implies that the respondents are not fully aware to the rock band or group of this music genre. On the other hand, there are a rock bands that have existed throughout the decades ever since the dawn of rock and roll, but the greatest ones have stood the test of time and continue to be classic and popular bands to listen to their timeless music so that the respondents are not familiar to the rock group of this genre, instead they are attractive in music when it is joyful, friendly, relaxed and calm.

Table 8. indicates the Level of Awareness on the Different Genres of Music. As seen from the table, the respondents are verbally interpreted fully aware in the different genres of music with the composite mean of 3.56. Most of the students aware in Rock Music which got a highest weighted mean of 3.69. This implies that the respondents are more familiar in rock music. This genre of music is attractive to teenagers. The study found that rock, the music of choice, made just about all the students „optimistic, joyful, friendly, relaxed and calm (Research Links Music and Listeners' Emotions, 2009).

Table 8. Summary Table on the Level of Awareness on the Different Genre of Music

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
Rap Music	3.43	Aware	5
Pop Music	3.59	Fully Aware	2
Classical Music	3.54	Fully Aware	4
Rhythm and Blues	3.57	Fully Aware	3

Rock Music	3.69	Fully Aware	1
Composite Mean	3.56	Fully Aware	

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 = Fully Aware; 2.50 – 3.49 = Aware; 1.50 – 2.49 = Slightly Aware; 1.00 – 1.49 = Not Aware

Next was Pop music which got a 3.59 weighted mean. The respondents were fully aware that the pop music were typically songs by the pop artist, this type of music should listen in radio, television, using technology rather than live performances. It has common instruments using by the pop artist include electric guitar, bass guitar, piano and the keyboard. According to Levitin (2010) the best artists have the capacity to make an interpretation of immaculate feeling into symphonious sound; consequently, many metal performers would populate this gathering. Additionally, the music would contain an overflow of feeling and immense affect a group of people that draws an association with some specific melody.

The Rhythm and Blues rank third and got a weighted mean of 3.57. The respondents are verbally interpreted fully aware that the rhythm and blues are like jazz music. The Classical Music got a weighted mean of 3.54 and it rank fourth and the respondents are verbally fully aware. Davis and Palladino (2009) Expressed that classical music is said to diminish stretch, melancholy, nervousness, and even actuate rest or enact the body. Albeit one can assuredly discover traditional music in the musical drama house, classical music is not bound to this one field. Traditional music for instance can be found in restoring offices, and in learning conditions.

The lowest and rank fifth was the Rap Music which got a weighted mean of 3.43. Rap music is known for its beat and its capacity to make individuals need to get up and move. It can be heard in numerous films and network shows and various specialists have won Grammy's for their achievements in making melodies that fit this mainstream sort. According to Devos (2010) the crucial beat of rap starts from hard funk rather than

Jamaican rhythms, and it is honest to goodness that there are fundamental complexities among rap and reggae. Regardless, the system actuating to the time of reggae and rap is essentially the same. The gifted laborers rap their lines to rhythms taken from records.

Table 9. Difference of Responses on the Level of Awareness on the Different Genre of Music When Grouped According to Profile Variables

Genre of Music	Sex		Age		Year Level	
	F-value	p-value	F-value	p-value	F-value	p-value
Rap Music	2.682*	0.008	0.663	0.516	1.359	0.255
Pop Music	4.863*	0.000	0.370	0.691	1.530	0.207
Rhythm and Blues	1.011	0.313	1.608	0.202	0.999	0.394
Classical Music	2.298*	0.022	0.173	0.841	2.219	0.086
Rock Music	2.775*	0.006	0.227	0.797	2.325	0.075

Legend: *Significant at-value < 0.05

Table 9 reveals that only sex shows significant difference on the level of awareness on the different genre of music (rap, pop, classical and rock music) when grouped according to sex. This was observed since the obtained p-values were all less than 0.05 alpha level. This means that male students viewed this genre of music differently compared with the female students.

According to Roszak (2010), numerous millennials are not yet presented to the assortment of melodic classifications that grown-ups might be. Moreover, they effectively dismiss many melodic classes to lighten the estrangement more pervasive in puberty level, which is having a few reasons. This idea of weakness alludes sentiment powerlessness to impact the powers that impact the individual's life shots.

Epstein (2016) said that youths, especially utilize music to help depict themselves. Numerous youngsters give music a focal place to their life. Basically, they utilize music to make their own subculture, recognized by the unmistakable qualities, convictions, and activities which youth utilize to go to, and to adapt to, their common social experience. For the most part in position to, and regularly in direct disagreement with, societal qualities, standards and desires. Subsequently, young people especially in male youths may hold fast to at least one melodic classis.

According to Christenson & Peterson [3] they found that even in by and large homogenous youth gathering of spectators there were two specific culture a male and a female. They found that males and females use and respond to music in different ways. Dees and Vera [4] found that music and its qualities suitable for an all-male and an all-female social event contrasted. Also, females were more probable utilize music as an optional satisfaction. Lott (2011) states that, young ladies raised to be ladylike, sustaining, and

put family before work, while guys, are raised to be autonomous, focused, and put individual objectives in front of social and family thought. Subsequently, youthful male, music regularly individual and of focal significance to their lives.

CONCLUSIONS

Majority of the respondents are female, ranging 14 – 16 years old and belong to Grade 10. The benefits of music for the respondents is that it provides a sense of achievement, happiness, and satisfaction to them. Among the five (5) different genre of music, they awareness was on rock music as millennials who are more exposed to this kind of music. Female is more adept in distinguishing the sounds and different genres of music.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The current and upcoming educators emphasize the rudiments and techniques in music and expose the students more on the different genres of music to acquaint on the variation of elements of music. The teacher may be equipped with audio of the different genre of music to enhance the listening skills of the students. And may expose the student on performing arts such as music, theater, film, dance, and cultural performances.

Table 10. Action Plan

OBJECTIVES	STRATEGIES/ ACTIVITIES	PERSONS INVOLVED	SUCCESS INDICATOR
1. To expose students on musical with different genre.	Provide a library of musical videos of different musical genre accessible to students. Field trip to different cultural musical presentations. Provide a musical room with pictures presentation of the different genre of music.	Teachers and students	Students can identify different variation of music through visual and audio devices.
2. To provide venue where the students can showcase their Talents in music.	Contests on the different genre.	Teachers and students	Recognition of talents.
3. To hone the expertise of the students on the rudiments and Techniques of music.	Teachers attend special trainings and seminars related to rudiments and techniques.	Teachers and students	Expertise of teachers handed down to students.

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